

IDENTITY AS THE BASIS OF PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY IN THE EDUCATION OF YOUTH IN CENTRAL ASIAN COUNTRIES

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Abstract. *The scientific article examines in detail the process of the development of pedagogy in the context of identity, the analysis of this science in the context of modern education and considers ways to formalize pedagogical knowledge. Identity in pedagogy as a long-term path of formation, having accumulated data and transformed into an extensive concept of teaching lessons. A basic academic extract that explores the common patterns of human learning, develops the basic principles of educational progress in general educational institutions of all kinds.*

Keywords: *pedagogy, identity, development of pedagogy, pedagogy, modern education, upbringing, general educational institutions.*

Аннотация. *В научной статье подробно рассматривается процесс развития педагогики в контексте идентичности, анализ данной науки в условиях современного образования и рассматриваются способы оформления педагогических знаний. Идентичность в педагогике как длительный путь формирования, накопив данные и преобразив в разветвленную концепцию преподавательских уроков. Базовой академической выдержкой, исследующей единые закономерности обучения человека, разрабатывающей основные принципы учебно-воспитательского хода в общеобразовательных учреждениях всех видов.*

Ключевые слова: *педагогика, идентичность, развитие педагогики, педагогика, современное образование, воспитание, общеобразовательные учреждения.*

Features of modern pedagogy in the education of students in the context of identity. Parenting is a complex, never-ending, constantly recurring multi-step process that is important in any field of human activity. Nevertheless, education has always been surrounded by certain unforeseen circumstances. This is how politics, times, social society, identity, worldview and cultural values change. Educating young people has never been an easy task. The educational process begins at birth, at home, in kindergarten and continues both at school and at university, since it occupies an important part in the life of modern students in education. As everyone knows, personality and identity develop in the environment of society, which contributes to the formation of moral qualities of values, principles and character. Modern pedagogy plays a very important role in the education of students, since the teacher needs not only to convey the necessary knowledge to students, but also to prepare them for passing the SRS, tests and exams. To create optimal conditions for students for self-improvement and self-realization, to form the necessary moral values and identities in education. Therefore, the role of modern pedagogy in the education of students is relevant to research and study.

Pedagogy includes four large areas: a) common basic principles of pedagogy; b) the concept of teaching (teaching); c) the concept of learning; d) the guidance of educational concepts.

In the past decades, according to these sections, it has grown to such an extent. They began to be emphasized by separate independent academic disciplines. A special category of teaching lessons that explore the specifics of educational activities from within specific age-related companies is age pedagogy [1, p. 3]. It contains preschool and preschool pedagogy, pedagogy of secondary educational institutions, pedagogy of higher education, pedagogy of seniors and androgogy, preschool pedagogy explores the patterns and requirements of teaching children under 3 years of age. Its mass is rapidly increasing according to the verge of the intrusion of an academic idea into the secrets of concentrated influence on the development of mental abilities, psychological and sensory areas of the child's personality, his well-being. A characteristic feature of nursery pedagogy is its connection with other branches of knowledge: psychology, physiology, medicine. Preschool pedagogy about the patterns of formation and development of the personality of a preschool child. There is a didactics of preschool education, the concept and methodology of teaching preschoolers, technological processes of teaching a child this year in state, individual, non-state educational organizations, in conditions of large, absolute, defective families. The pedagogy of secondary educational institutions explores the patterns of teaching and learning of a school-age child. It belongs to the most well-formed branches of the education lesson. Pedagogy of higher education the patterns of the educational process in the circumstances of the highest educational institution, the characteristic difficulties of obtaining. Senior pedagogy and androgogy follow the characteristic features of activities with adults and the elderly. Pedagogical excerpts are divided depending on which side of a particular type of human work is borrowed into the systematization database. There are musical, industrial pedagogy, correctional labor pedagogy, stage pedagogy, and museum pedagogy. Industrial pedagogy explores the patterns of teaching workers, improving their skills, and retraining for new specialties. The pedagogy of impeccable technological creation presupposes a branch of science, the object of which is considered to be the patterns of training highly qualified workers. The teaching disciplines include: chronicle of pedagogy, comparative pedagogy, ethno pedagogy, ideology of education, public pedagogy, pedagogical psychology, social studies, etc. The history of pedagogy studies the emergence and formation of educational practice, teaching concepts, unified and individual methodological concepts in various significant periods and stages. Understanding the event of pedagogy should be in order to become more aware of the problems being solved today. Comparative pedagogy is interested in considering and comparing the creation in different countries [1, p. 201].

Until the 90s of the last century, the school assumed the responsibility of educating students, since the main goal of the state was the formation of certain Soviet values. Since the end of the 20th century, it has been decided that teachers are not obliged to carry out educational activities for students, but to teach them only according to the school curriculum. Then all the upbringing was transferred to the parents. With the onset of the economic and political crisis, the divergence of moral principles among the community, and the lack of civic values and tolerance among young people, government agencies began to think about the importance of identity and youth education. Modern pedagogy is limited to a certain range of possibilities. The purpose of training and education of modern students is not only to study according to the program, but also the comprehensive development of personality, such as independence, responsibility, self-realization, self-discipline, etc. Modern pedagogy in the educational process has the following possibilities: most modern teachers understand the importance of education as society is in a deplorable state. Which affects the lack of tolerance, and the decline of moral and civic values. All

problems of an educational nature must be immediately discussed and resolved not only at home, but also in all educational institutions.

Analysis of the educational market in Central Asian Countries Higher education is crucial for social and economic development. Higher education is seen as a decisive factor in economic development in four Central Asian countries - Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Uzbekistan, which have committed themselves to move from an economy based on natural resources to a "knowledge society" [3]. This is evidenced by the strategy "Kazakhstan-2050" of the Republic of Kazakhstan[4], aimed at expanding employment opportunities; The National Development Strategy of the Kyrgyz Republic, the main goal of which is the development of human potential [5]; The National Development Strategy of the Republic of Tajikistan for the period up to 2030, which considers higher education as a means of preparing students to enter the labor market; and the National Action Strategy for the Development of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, which, among other reforms, provides for the referral of 90% of students to vocational education [3] to increase employment, while contributing to the liberalization and modernization of the economy [6]. Quality of education – According to the UNESCO Analytical Note "Higher Education in Central Asia" (Almaty, 2021), of the four Central Asian countries (Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan), only Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan have implemented independent accreditation. The national [3] education policies and plans of these countries lack accountability mechanisms for quality control of higher education in private educational institutions. In Central Asia and the Asia-Pacific region as a whole, there is also a marked discrepancy between education and the requirements of the modern market, with almost 50% of employers in the region reporting that they face difficulties filling vacant positions. The inconsistency of education with the requirements of the modern market is not just the result of inadequate education, but a consequence of the need to reform the education sector at the systemic level to meet the needs of the labor market. From the point of view of ensuring the quality of education in general, there are, among other things, such problems as the lack of involvement of employers, as well as professional organizations in the processes of ensuring the quality of education and mechanisms to predict the level of market demand for specific professions. The state of higher education in Central Asia The countries of Central Asia are at different stages of development in the field of higher education, with marked differences in the level of education coverage, completion rates and coverage of public and private educational institutions. There are also differences in the level of internationalization of higher education and employment opportunities. Gross enrolment ratios (GCE) in higher education vary in the region from 62% in Kazakhstan to 41% in Kyrgyzstan, 31% in Tajikistan and 10% in Uzbekistan. [3] Based on the East Kazakhstan Region, countries at the global level are classified into the following three stages of growth: [6] 1) elite stage – access to higher education is limited to high-income people or those with outstanding talents (East Kazakhstan region at the level of 15% or lower); 2) mass stage – higher education is available to a wider range of the population (East Kazakhstan region from 16 to 50%); 3) universal stage – higher education is a common path of development for many young people (East Kazakhstan region above 51%) Source: UNESCO, Analytical Note on Central Asia 2022: [3]. Higher education completion rates are defined as the percentage of people aged 25-29 and 30-34 who have completed at least two to four years of higher education. The corresponding national average in Central Asia is 52% in Kazakhstan, 37% in Kyrgyzstan, 21% in Tajikistan and 10% in Uzbekistan [3] The number of higher education institutions (universities) also varies. The largest number of universities in Kazakhstan is 125, of which 30 are state-owned.

Today, universities have become centers for training highly qualified personnel to provide all sectors of the national economy, kindergartens, schools, higher educational institutions, local government and public administration, as well as personnel from the private and non-governmental sectors. Research activities are carried out on an equal basis with education. A distinctive feature of such universities was that their education was aimed mainly at the accumulation of knowledge. Today, there has been an objective replacement of the thesis "education for life" with "lifelong learning", when education does not end with a diploma and a profession. In a rapidly changing world, the key role is played by the so-called "flexible" skills of the future: emotional intelligence, media literacy, the ability to improve oneself and learn, flexibility and creativity. The main basic education of the XXI century is the ability to self-improvement and self-learning. It is obvious that the modern universities of the republic are no longer the same as they were 20-30 years ago. Time forces universities to transform and develop in order to always meet the requirements of world education. The school provides for the education of students in society, it is in it that a person develops, personality and character are formed, moral principles and values are formed. Accordingly, the task of the teacher is to guide students correctly, not to allow bullying, not to be indifferent to the problems of the younger generation. In addition, the teacher must monitor how his own contact with the students takes place, how it develops, what he says, what kind of example he sets.

Modern pedagogy has a lot of opportunities for the versatile development of students. You can organize extracurricular activities, interest groups, educational workshops, psychological trainings. The main thing is the desire of the teacher to positively influence students and invest his own efforts in the formation of their personalities and identity. The modern generation values their rights and freedom of choice very much, therefore it is important to build the educational process according to the principle of democracy. The teacher should interact with students, and the educational process is structured in such a way that there is an atmosphere of mutual understanding and support. A teacher is not a bearer of rules and theorems, but an important person involved in the life of a child and the formation of his personality and identity. A greater effect can be achieved if you create free interaction between the university and parents, with regard to the educational process. If teachers and parents, the child's family will make joint efforts for education, it will be possible to achieve good results.

In addition to opportunities, modern pedagogy has limitations that sometimes negatively affect the educational process and the formation of identity. The acute problem is that the political and social crisis directly affects the school. Education is designed to build a scale of values. Since Kyrgyz education is inclusive, students from completely different families, as well as with different financial status, health status, etc. can study in the same group. Because of this, modern pedagogy cannot build an effective educational program for everyone. An equally important problem is that we teach teachers according to the old program focused on the generation of the last century. Modern students are very different from their ancestors, and every year they move further and further away from the university. Accordingly, the current generation requires a modern approach to the educational process. Students increasingly began to focus on the culture and values of Western countries, losing their existing identities. Basically, teachers cannot understand the true desires of students, find a common language with them, sometimes they do not understand the essence of the problems and very often devalue them. Computer technology and the Internet are increasingly replacing live communication, so students prefer the virtual world to school events. The main reason why students rush to sit out the required number of lessons and

run home, abandoning various clubs and extracurricular activities. Moreover, the authorities evaluate the effectiveness of the educational process, focusing on the number of events held and the documentation filled out by teachers on this occasion. Accordingly, due to the extensive work with the papers of teachers, there is not enough time to carry out really effective educational activities.

Conclusion. Modern pedagogy plays an important role in the education of students. It is important to move on to new systems and principles that allow you to grow independent individuals with values and life orientations. A special category of teaching lessons is designed in this way by individual, subject-based technologies that study the patterns of learning and studying specific training disciplines in absolutely all types of educational and general educational bodies. On the rights and freedoms of students, an atmosphere of mutual understanding, support and respect. It allows you to educate holistic individuals with normal psychological health who respect not only their personal boundaries, but also the opinions and interests of other people. The internal concept of the teaching lesson, the emergence of new industries that are generated by the formation of community and academic knowledge. Personality is formed by development, which leads to a formation oriented towards processes that have not yet been formed, but are in a period of development.

Recommendations for further development:

- Development of comparable National Qualifications Frameworks: comparison of the level of training of specialists in general and by individual industries.
- optimization of the recognition procedure for educational documents, academic degrees and titles: development of recommendations on recognition procedures.
- Ensuring the quality of education in order to develop comparable criteria and methodologies: analysis and comparison of quality assurance procedures, mutual learning activities.
- cooperation in the development of educational programs, joint training programs, practical training and scientific research: creation of pilot and scientific projects, and further dissemination of experience.
- Participation in meetings of the Central Asian Group on Global Policy Dialogue and making proposals for regional cooperation.
- Development strategy for 5 years (priorities, directions of development, indicators, SWOT analysis), taking into account the Turkestan Declaration, Recommendations of rectors of Central Asian countries, the Work Plan of universities of Central Asian countries.
- Work plan for the next 3 years (defining tasks, developing indicators, conducting monitoring, joint projects).
- Creation of working groups (development of technical specifications for groups, selection of experts, approval of work plans) quality assurance.
- Creation and maintenance of an information portal (news, background information, documents).

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